

Supplementary Methods

Pre-processing genomic DNA sequence reads

To remove erroneous bases from the genomic DNA sequence data, we performed adapter and quality trimming using Cutadapt¹ (version 1.18). We clipped sequences that matched at least 90% of the total length of one of the adapter sequences provided in the NEBNext Multiplex Oligos for Illumina (Index Primers Set 1). In addition, we trimmed bases from the 5' and 3' ends of reads if they had a phred score of 20 or lower. Reads that were shorter than 100 bp after trimming were discarded.

Trimmed reads were aligned to a modified version of the *A. thaliana* Col-0 reference genome (TAIR10, European Nucleotide Accession number: GCA_000001735.2) which contained an improved assembly of the mitochondrial sequence (Sequence Read Archive accession number: BK010421)² using bwa mem³ (version 0.7.10-r789) with default parameters. The resulting alignment files were sorted and indexed using samtools⁴ (version 1.3.1). We merged alignment files of libraries generated from the same accession using Picard MarkDuplicates, which was called through the GATK suite⁵ (version 4.0.2.1). MarkDuplicates was also used to mark duplicate read pairs, using an optical duplicate pixel distance of 2500, as recommended in its documentation when working with patterned Illumina flowcells of the HiSeq 4000 platform.

We assessed whether each accession had adequate coverage to perform variant calling by computing the number of aligned bases of each accession using GATK CollectAlignmentSummaryMetrics. Each dataset had at least 28x coverage (Figure S9), which should be sufficient to accurately call SNPs, indels, and CNVs in a diploid plant species such as *A. thaliana*.

Filtering SNPs and indels

We filtered sets of SNPs and indels using two complementary approaches to remove likely false positive calls. First, we filtered the nuclear callset using GATK VariantRecalibrator and GATK ApplyVQSQR (parameter `-truth-sensitivity-filter-level` set at 99.9). The set of variants called in a world-wide panel of 1135 *A. thaliana* accessions (described in REF.⁶) were used as a training and truth set (prior=10.0) during recalibration. Second, we filtered variants using a set of hard thresholds as described in the documentation of GATK (<https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035531112?id=6925>). In order to choose appropriate thresholds, we generated density plots of six variant annotations known to be informative for identifying false positive calls (QD, FS, SOR, MQ, MQRankSum, and ReadPosRankSum) using a large set of SNPs and indels called in 1,506 *A. thaliana* samples of the 1,001 Genomes collection⁶, an African collection⁷, a Chinese collection⁸, and a collection sampled from Madeira⁹. To assess the effect of the filtering steps, we computed the percentage of SNV calls removed from each sample after filtering using Picard CollectVariantCallingMetrics (<https://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>) (version 2.9.2). Most variants were retained after filtering (Figure S10), indicating that the majority of called SNPs are likely true positives.

Post-processing and validation of CNVs

CNV sites in each accession were genotyped by computing the read depth at the sites, relative to the rest of the chromosome they are located on, using duphold¹⁰ (v0.1.1).

Deletion sites were considered to be homozygous if they had a relative read depth lower than 0.25, heterozygous if they had a relative read depth between 0.25 and 0.75, and non-variant if they had a read depth higher than 0.75. Tandem and dispersed duplication sites were considered homozygous if they had a relative read depth higher than 1.75, heterozygous if they had a relative read depth between 1.25 and 1.75, and non-variant if they had a read depth below 1.25. As we cannot determine the genotype of insertions based on read depth, insertions were assigned a genotype of unknown/variant (./1) by default. After genotyping each site in each accession, we merged the call sets of each individual sample, merging CNVs that are likely to correspond to the same event. CNV calls were merged if they fulfilled the following conditions: they were of the same type; their breakpoints were located within 1000 bp of each other on both the 5' and 3' end; they share at least 50% reciprocal overlap with each other (does not apply to insertions); and the distance between the insertion sites is no more than 10 bp (only applies to dispersed duplications and insertions). The regions of the merged calls are defined as the union of the regions of the original calls. For instance, one call that covers positions 12-30 and a call that covers positions 14-32 are merged into a call covering positions 12-32. We excluded calls that were not supported by a change in read depth in any accession, as these are likely false positives.

Hecaton uses a random forest model to integrate the output of different callers and estimates a posterior probability estimate for CNVs, filtering those that fall below a certain threshold. To explore the effect of the filtering threshold, we generated sets using three different settings: 0.7, 0.75, and 0.8. No insertions were reported at thresholds of 0.75 and 0.8 (Figure S11), as these are difficult to accurately detect using short reads and therefore assigned a low probability. To include this type of CNV in our analysis, we chose to perform all further analyses using the set generated at a threshold of 0.7.

As sets of CNVs detected from short reads may contain spurious numbers of false positives and negatives¹¹, we evaluated the sensitivity and precision of our detection approach by checking whether deletions reported in accessions were supported by a matching decrease in read depth. We were not able to use this method to assess the sensitivity and precision for duplications and insertions, as the expected increase in read depth at the affected regions can be caused by a number of other factors besides CNV, such as spurious alignments of reads in repetitive genomic regions. Read depth of regions predicted to be deleted in samples, relative to the 1000 bp flanks of such regions, was computed using duphold. Homozygous deletion calls were considered to be likely false positives if they had a relative read depth higher than 0.25, heterozygous deletions calls if they had a relative read depth lower than 0.25 or higher than 0.75, and non-variant calls if they had a read depth lower than 0.75. Note that the error rates computed using this method can be considered an upper bound, because reads of a sample may also fail to map to a region if it contains a large number of SNPs and indels in the sample genome relative to the reference¹².

Investigating the effect of sequencing protocol on pairwise genetic distance

To investigate to what extent genetic distance between samples was influenced by differences in sequencing protocol, we modeled the genetic distance between different samples as a function of several technical co-variates. For each pair of samples i and

j , we assume that the genetic distance D_{ij} is linearly dependent on differences in sequencing coverage C_{ij} , sequencing platform P_{ij} , insert size I_{ij} , and read length R_{ij} :

$$D_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 C_{ij} + \beta_2 P_{ij} + \beta_3 I_{ij} + \beta_4 R_{ij}$$

β parameters were estimated with the MRM function of the R `ecodist` package¹³ (v2.0.1), using genetic distances computed from the 1,506 *A. thaliana* samples used to define false positive SNP and indel calls. For the co-variate “sequencing platform”, we assigned a 1 to a sample if it was sequenced using Hiseq 3000 or a more recent platform, otherwise we assigned a 0. The reason for choosing Hiseq 3000 as a cut-off point is that Illumina platforms started using different flowcells (patterned instead of non-patterned) from that point on. We excluded insert size while modeling genetic distance based on SNPs, as not all samples were sequenced using paired-end libraries.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: **CNVs in the DartMap panel.** (a) Size distribution of CNVs. CNVs below 50 bp are excluded, as these are considered indels. (b) Type distribution of CNVs: deletions (DEL), insertions (INS), tandem duplications (DUP:TAN), or dispersed duplications (DUP:DIS).

Figure S2: **Deletions in the DartMap panel were called with high precision.** The y-axis shows the percentage of genotype calls supported by a matching decrease (non-reference allele) or no change (reference allele) in read depth. Deletion variant sites are stratified along the x-axis by frequency of the non-reference (deletion) allele.

Figure S3: **Dendrograms based on organellar variation.** (a-b) Dendrograms constructed based on pairwise similarity of chloroplast (a) and mitochondrial (b) variants between Dutch accessions and those of nearby countries.

Figure S4: **Dendrogram of group 1 based on nuclear variation.** At its highest level, the dendrogram constructed based on pairwise similarity of nuclear variants between Dutch accessions and those of nearby countries can be split into two groups. Group 1 and its three subgroups (1a, 1b, and 1c) are depicted here.

Figure S5: **Dendrogram of group 2 based on nuclear variation.** At its highest level, the dendrogram constructed based on pairwise similarity of nuclear variants between Dutch accessions and those of nearby countries can be split into two groups. Group 2 and its three subgroups (2a, 2b, and 2c) are depicted here.

Figure S6: **Iron deficiency GWAS time series.** Summary data of the GWA results over 10 time points, measured during days 17 and 18 after sowing for three different phenotypes: [1] the average Φ_{PSII} per accession in iron deficient conditions (grey), [2] the ratio between Φ_{PSII} in iron deficient conditions and Φ_{PSII} in control conditions (orange), and [3] the residuals (blue). The dots on the graph represent the highest LOD scores in a 25 kb window size above a LOD threshold of 6. The * represents the data from the Manhattan plot in Figure ??b.

Figure S7: **Gene expression levels per haplotype group as measured by RT-qPCR.** The average gene expression levels at (21 μM Fe^{2+} (Control, depicted in dark grey) and (1 μM Fe^{2+}) (Low iron, depicted in orange) per haplotype group for two iron deficiency marker genes (a), nine candidate genes from the GWAS (b) and two splice variants of *FSD3* (c). Average gene expression levels were taken from six natural accessions (with 5 replicates per accession per treatment) and normalized relative to three reference genes (*SAND*, *YLS8*, and *TIP41-like*). Significance of differences was assessed using two-sample t-tests on all Ct values from both treatments per haplotype. Error bars represent SE. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure S8: **Population structure of *A. thaliana* in Sweden and the Iberian peninsula.** (a) Dendrogram of Swedish accessions. (b) Dendrogram of Iberian accessions. (c) Geographical location of groups of Swedish accessions after cutting the dendrogram into two clusters. Groups correspond to accessions sampled in the north and south, as previously reported¹⁴. (d) Geographical location of groups of Iberian accessions after cutting the dendrogram into three clusters. The two outgroups of that are distinct from the majority correspond to relicts and accessions sampled in mountains, as previously reported¹⁵.

Figure S9: **Genomic coverage of each Dutch accession after pre-processing.** All samples have at least 28x coverage.

Figure S10: **Effect of filtering steps on number of retained SNPs for each sample.** The percentage of filtered SNPs is shown for the mitochondrial (a), chloroplast (b), and nuclear (c) callsets. The y-axes show the number of samples in which a particular percentage of SNPs (x-axes) were filtered.

Figure S11: **Number and types of CNV detected at different cut-offs of Hecaton.** Insertions were not reported at high cut-offs, as Hecaton generally considers them to be inaccurate.

References

1. Martin, M. Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *EMBnet.journal* **17**, 10–12 (2011).
2. Sloan, D. B., Wu, Z. & Sharbrough, J. Correction of persistent errors in Arabidopsis reference mitochondrial genomes. *The Plant Cell* **30**, 525–527 (2018).
3. Li, H. Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with BWA-MEM. Preprint at <http://arxiv.org/abs/1207.3907> (2013).
4. Li, H. *et al.* The sequence alignment/map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2078–2079 (2009).
5. McKenna, A. *et al.* The Genome Analysis Toolkit: a MapReduce framework for analyzing next-generation DNA sequencing data. *Genome Research* **20**, 1297–1303 (2010).
6. The 1001 Genomes Consortium. 1,135 genomes reveal the global pattern of polymorphism in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Cell* **166**, 481–491 (2016).
7. Durvasula, A. *et al.* African genomes illuminate the early history and transition to selfing in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **114**, 5213–5218 (2017).
8. Zou, Y.-P. *et al.* Adaptation of *Arabidopsis thaliana* to the Yangtze River basin. *Genome Biology* **18**, 239 (2017).
9. Fulgione, A., Koornneef, M., Roux, F., Hermisson, J. & Hancock, A. M. Madeiran *Arabidopsis thaliana* reveals ancient long-range colonization and clarifies demography in Eurasia. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* **35**, 564–574 (2017).
10. Pedersen, B. S. & Quinlan, A. R. Duphold: scalable, depth-based annotation and curation of high-confidence structural variant calls. *GigaScience* **8**, giz040 (2019).
11. Cameron, D. L., Di Stefano, L. & Papenfuss, A. T. Comprehensive evaluation and characterisation of short read general-purpose structural variant calling software. *Nature Communications* **10**, 1–11 (2019).
12. Schneeberger, K. *et al.* Simultaneous alignment of short reads against multiple genomes. *Genome Biology* **10**, R98 (2009).
13. Goslee, S. C., Urban, D. L., *et al.* The ecodist package for dissimilarity-based analysis of ecological data. *Journal of Statistical Software* **22**, 1–19 (2007).
14. Long, Q. *et al.* Massive genomic variation and strong selection in *Arabidopsis thaliana* lines from Sweden. *Nature Genetics* **45**, 884 (2013).
15. Tabas-Madrid, D. *et al.* Genome-wide signatures of flowering adaptation to climate temperature: Regional analyses in a highly diverse native range of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant, Cell & Environment* **41**, 1806–1820 (2018).